

PROJECT DETAILS

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Summary

This report presents the **validation results** of forest disturbance maps produced under the RIGOR-MED project, focusing on the Iberian Peninsula and surrounding Mediterranean regions. It assesses the accuracy of both internal (Landsat and Sentinel-2) and external (GFC, EFDA, AACS) datasets, as well as two harmonized products generated through source-priority and class-priority fusion strategies. The evaluation is based on a robust reference dataset of nearly 2,800 sample units and over 3,400 interpreted disturbance polygons, derived through systematic visual analysis of multi-sensor satellite imagery.

The validation approach combines unit-level confusion matrices with pixel-based detection metrics, applying consistent protocols across multiple definitions of "change" (from abrupt events to more inclusive criteria). The assessment reveals that while individual products perform adequately within their operational scope, they tend to suffer from high omission rates, particularly when detecting subtle or progressive disturbances such as thinning or shrub clearing. Among the individual datasets, Landsat and Sentinel demonstrate relatively strong spatial sensitivity but are conservative in detecting change, whereas AACS is more responsive but prone to over-detection.

Harmonized products clearly outperform all others in both binary and thematic classification accuracy, achieving balanced detection rates, zero commission errors, and high robustness across all validation scenarios. The fusion logic applied in the harmonization—particularly the source-priority approach—proves effective in improving thematic consistency, especially for identifying harvest-related changes. Nonetheless, challenges remain in detecting low-severity or small-scale disturbances, which are frequently overlooked across all mapping approaches.

Overall, this deliverable confirms the added value of harmonized, multi-source forest disturbance maps for Mediterranean ecosystems.

1 Reference Dataset Description

The reference data is composed of two primary layers: a set of **sample units** ($n = 2,796$) uniformly distributed across 13 European countries (Southern and Central Europe), and a corresponding set of **disturbance polygons** ($n = 3,453$) mapped through visual interpretation of multi-source satellite imagery. Each polygon is linked to the sample unit in which it was detected.

The **sampling units** themselves were stratified across ecological gradients and forest types, with each unit defined as a **250 × 250 m square**. Units with no observed disturbance were explicitly marked as “No Change”, ensuring completeness and allowing for binary validation alongside thematic evaluations. The sampling frame and interpretation protocol were harmonized through collaborative work with the University of Florence. A key step in this process included independent reinterpretation of 10% of the Spanish and Portuguese units by multiple analysts, to ensure alignment of interpretation criteria.

The classification protocol followed a disturbance typology tailored to Mediterranean forest conditions, with particular attention paid to the distinction between **abrupt events** (such as clear-cutting or fire) and more **subtle or diffuse phenomena** (like thinning or shrub clearing). **Interpretation was conducted using the Collect Earth Online (CEO) platform**, enabling seamless integration of **high-resolution and medium-resolution imagery** (Landsat, Sentinel-2, PlanetScope), and allowing the use of ancillary information to improve attribution. The database documents disturbances over a **23-year period (2000–2023)**, enabling the validation of both historical and recent forest change products.

Finally, all reference data were structured for use in geospatial analysis environments, with a dual output system: spatial geometries (polygons) and corresponding tabular attributes, linked via unique plot identifiers. This structure facilitated subsequent harmonization, reclassification, and filtering operations required for fair and meaningful validation of the diverse set of products assessed in RIGOR-MED.

Among the sample units analyzed, **1,610 units were labelled as affected by a forest disturbance event**, based on visual interpretation. The most frequently assigned disturbance types are **clear-cutting (almost 800 cases)** and **thinning (around 600 cases)**, followed by more localized occurrences of **shrub clearing (86)** and **fire (71)**. A small number of plots were confirmed to have **no change** despite being visually reviewed, mainly in countries like Bosnia and Serbia.

Spain accounts for **650 sample units**, of which **294** were labelled with disturbance, distributed across various categories: 135 clear-cutting, 13 fire, 52 shrubs clearing, and 94 thinning. This makes Spain the most represented country in terms of both overall units and interpreted change events, reflecting the project's geographic focus and national monitoring needs.

The comparative analysis of reference data across countries highlights notable differences in the incidence and typology of forest disturbances. While **Italy, Turkey, and Bulgaria** account for the highest absolute number of affected sampling units, **Portugal** emerges as the country with the **highest relative proportion** of disturbed units (56.8%), followed by **Macedonia (38.9%)** and **Bulgaria (37.5%)**. In contrast, **Spain**, despite being the country with the largest total number of units and disturbance polygons, shows a more moderate relative disturbance rate of **27.7%**.

Regarding disturbance types, **clear-cutting** is the dominant class in most countries and accounts for more than 70% of disturbances in **Portugal**, and over 60% in **Croatia** and **Greece**. **Thinning** is prevalent in countries with more intensive forest management, such as **Italy, Bosnia**, and **Bulgaria**, while **shrub clearing** is a distinctive feature in **Spain**, representing nearly **one fifth** of its recorded disturbances. Fires are less frequent overall but show regional concentration in **Albania** and **Greece**.

These patterns reflect the diversity of ecological contexts and forest management practices across the Mediterranean and highlight the importance of disaggregated analysis when validating forest change detection products.

Table 1. Reference database used for validation. Counts of sampled interpretation units per country, disaggregated into change types—clear-cutting, wildfire, shrub clearing, and thinning—plus “No change.” The last column reports the number (and percentage) of sampled units that show any change.

Country	Total Sample Units	Clear-cutting	Fire	Shrub clearing	Thinning	Units No Change	Sample Units with Changes
Albania	36	4	5	1	1	28	8 (22.2%)
Bosnia and Herzegovina	133	22	3	1	27	92	41 (30.8 %)
Bulgaria	280	77	0	1	79	175	105 (37.5 %)
Croatia	117	28	0	1	18	86	31 (26,5)
Greece	215	42	10	2	15	170	45 (20.9 %)
Italy	540	110	11	9	253	339	201 (37.2 %)
Macedonia	72	33	4	1	7	44	28 (38.9 %)
Montenegro	27	4	2	0	3	21	6 (22.2 %)
Portugal	111	139	14	13	25	48	63 (56.8 %)
Serbia	166	69	1	1	30	113	53 (31.9 %)
Slovenia	72	17	0	0	11	54	18 (25.0 %)
Spain	650	135	13	52	94	470	180 (27.7 %)
Turkey	377	108	8	4	44	258	119 (32.1%)
Total	2,796					1,898	898

2 Overview of Maps Products Evaluated

A diverse set of forest disturbance maps has been assembled for validation within the RIGOR-MED project, each of them generated using distinct methodologies, sensors, and spatial-temporal resolutions. These products differ not only in their capacity to detect changes but also in the way they classify and characterize disturbance events, ranging from simple binary legends (change/no-change) to more thematically detailed classifications.

The **internal products** include annual disturbance maps generated from **Landsat imagery (2018–2023)** (here after *Landsat*) and **Sentinel-2 imagery (2020–2023)** hereafter (*Sentinel-2*), both derived using the Continuous Change Detection and Classification (CCDC) algorithm combined with Random Forest classification. These maps are thematically rich, offering classification into four distinct disturbance types: **clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, and wildfires**.

In contrast to the internal maps, three **external products** have been selected as benchmarks for comparative validation and harmonization:

1. **Global Forest Change (GFC)** by Hansen et al. provides annual global estimates of tree cover loss at 30-meter resolution since 2000 to 2023. While globally consistent and frequently updated, GFC offers only binary change detection and lacks thematic attribution regarding disturbance type.
2. The **European Forest Disturbance Atlas (EFDA)**, offers annual pan-European maps of forest disturbances (1983-2023), distinguishing specific drivers such as fire or harvest.
3. The **Alert and Annual Change System (AACS)**, a national vector-based product from Spain (2020-2023), delivers near-real-time detection of forest disturbances. It includes the following legend: vegetation loss and wildfires.

Given the heterogeneity of the maps used, the project developed **two harmonized disturbance layers**. This harmonization process was not just a technical necessity to address product inconsistency, but a strategic choice to **leverage the complementary strengths** of each dataset. To enable integration, a unified classification schema (**Table 2**) was established with seven harmonized classes: 0 (no data), 1 (no change), 2 (clear-cutting), 3 (canopy decrease), 4 (shrub clearing), 5 (fire), and 6 (unknown).

A special classification procedure was implemented for EFDA logging events, where the assignment to either clear-cutting (class 2) or canopy decrease (class 3) depended on the associated EFDA severity data. Prior probabilities for clear-cutting versus canopy decrease were calculated based on the relative frequency of these classes in the Landsat source. Beta distributions were then fitted to the severity values of pixels where Landsat and EFDA agreed (clear-cut or thinning in Landsat and logging in EFDA). Using Bayes' rule, each EFDA logging pixel was assigned to the class with higher posterior probability given its severity value. When insufficient training data was available (fewer than 10 pixels per class), default beta distribution parameters were used.

Table 2. Harmonization rules from source legends to the common legend. Mapping of original classes from each source dataset to the harmonized classes used in this assessment. For each source, the table lists the original label and the corresponding harmonized label (e.g., No data → No data; No change → No change; Clear-cutting/Thinning/Shrub clearing/Wildfire → same class; dataset-specific labels like "Tree cover loss" → harmonized category as specified).

Source Dataset	Original class	Harmonized class
Landsat and Sentinel Annual disturbances maps from time series	No data	No data
	No change	No change
	Clear-cutting	Clear-cutting
	Thinning	Thinning
	Shrub clearing	Shrub clearing
	Wildfire	Wildfire
GFC (Global Forest Change)	Tree cover loss	Unknown
EFDA (European Forest Disturbance Atlas)	No change	No change
	Wind	Unknown
	Logging	Clear-cut/Thinning
	Wildfire	Wildfire
AACs (Alert and Annual Change System) Spain	Wildfire	Wildfire
	Vegetation loss	Unknown

These sources were combined following two harmonization strategies.

- **Strategy A (Source-Priority Approach):** This method establishes a hierarchical voting system with predefined source priorities (EFDA > Landsat > AACs > Sentinel > GFC). Fire detections from AACs are given absolute priority and immediately returned. The algorithm requires at least two sources to indicate change before proceeding to mark change. Among change classes (2-5, excluding unknown), the most frequently detected class is identified. In cases of ties, the source hierarchy determines the final classification, with higher-priority sources taking precedence.
- **Strategy B (Class-Priority Approach):** This strategy implements a class-based hierarchy (fire > clear cutting > canopy decrease > shrub clearing > unknown > no change > no data) after initial vote counting. Similar to Strategy A, fire detections from AACs receive immediate priority, and at least two sources must detect change before marking a change. However, when multiple change classes receive equal votes, the predetermined class hierarchy determines the output rather than source priority.

3 Validation Methodology

The validation of forest disturbance products in RIGOR-MED was carried out using a structured, multi-layered approach, designed to compare map outputs with a curated reference dataset

under consistent and reproducible conditions. The analysis focused on **Spain**, the country with the most representative sample, and was conducted across both a **common time frame (2020–2023)** and the **specific operational horizon for each product**.

The core evaluation was based on **confusion matrices**, constructed by comparing the reference class of each interpreted disturbance polygon or undisturbed sample unit with the majority class assigned by each map to the same spatial footprint. For each year, accuracy metrics including Overall Accuracy (OA), Omission Error (1 – Producer’s Accuracy), and Commission Error (1 – User’s Accuracy) were derived. In products with sufficient thematic resolution, **class-specific validation** was conducted, reporting performance per disturbance type.

Given the differences in thematic legends and detection objectives among the evaluated products, several **adaptations** were introduced to ensure **fair comparison**:

- For **binary products** such as GFC, polygons labeled as shrub clearing or thinning were excluded from the validation, as these disturbance types fall outside the scope of abrupt change detection.
- For **products with limited thematic detail**, like EFDA and AACCS, the class “shrubs clearing” was also excluded, while clear-cutting, thinning and fire were retained.
- **Class harmonization** was applied to all maps to align product-specific labels with a common ontology, allowing results to be grouped under “abrupt change” (e.g., clear-cutting and fire), aggregated into “change” versus “no change” or grouped under “harvest”, “fire” and no change.

In parallel, a complementary pixel-level performance analysis was implemented. This approach evaluated detection consistency within each reference polygon, based on the proportion of pixels classified as disturbed. For each polygon, additional metrics were extracted:

- **Detection rate**: proportion of disturbed polygons where at least one pixel was flagged as change.
- **Average detection area**: share of pixels classified as disturbed within the polygon.
- **Temporal accuracy**: difference (in years) between the reference disturbance date and the detected one.
- **False positive rate**: proportion of disturbed pixels detected within undisturbed reference units.

While this approach provides valuable insight into internal detection dynamics, it typically results in higher detection rates compared to those derived from confusion matrices. This is due to the fact that even partial detections (i.e., one or two disturbed pixels) are counted as successful under this method, whereas confusion matrices rely on majority vote and stricter one-to-one agreement at the unit level.

Consequently, both methods offer complementary perspectives: confusion matrices enable standardized accuracy metrics and thematic comparison, while pixel-level summaries provide a more detailed view of spatial sensitivity, temporal alignment, and detection reliability across polygon sizes.

4 Results

4.1 Binary Change Detection Accuracy

4.1.1 Reference period: 2020-2023

All metrics reported below refer exclusively to the common validation period from 2020 to 2023, during which all products were available and evaluated under harmonized spatial and thematic conditions. To ensure fair comparison, each product was assessed under three different definitions of “change” in the reference dataset:

1. A **product-specific** definition, where only the disturbance types that each map was designed to detect were included:
 - **Landsat, Sentinel**, and the two **Harmonized maps** distinguish five disturbance classes: **clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, fire, and unknown**. All five were considered as valid “change” types in their evaluation.
 - **GFC** is a binary product designed to detect abrupt loss; only **clear-cutting and wildfire** were retained.
 - **AACS** includes vegetation loss and fire detection, thus, **clear-cutting and wildfire** were evaluated accordingly.
 - **EFDA** reports harvest and wildfires, therefore, it was evaluated under the assumption that clear-cutting, thinning and wildfires represent valid changes.
2. A **restricted definition**, limited to abrupt events only: **clear-cutting and fire**.
3. An **inclusive definition**, encompassing **clear-cutting, fire, and thinning**, thus reflecting a broader spectrum of forest management practices and gradual canopy reductions.

4.1.1.1 Product-specific definition

This first validation setup evaluates each map using a disturbance definition aligned with its native legend and design scope. As such, it is not intended to directly compare products with different thematic domains but to measure **internal consistency and accuracy under ideal conditions**. Results show relatively high overall accuracies across the board, with several products achieving zero commission error for change (e.g. GFC, Landsat). However, omission errors remain substantial, indicating that even within their own operational range, most products fail to detect a large portion of known disturbances. Only the **Harmonized layers and AACS achieve a more balanced profile**, though AACS shows a high false positive rate, possibly due to thematic mismatch.

The high overall accuracy of **GFC (97.99%)** and its absence of commission errors for change might at first appear indicative of strong performance. However, this metric conceals a fundamental limitation: GFC registers only the **first disturbance** detected in a pixel. Subsequent events, such as salvage logging after fire or thinning following clear-cutting, remain invisible. This design choice leads to significant omission (35.71%) despite apparent precision.

Landsat, with 95.41% overall accuracy and 0% commission error for change, exhibits a similarly conservative pattern, failing to capture many reference disturbances (omission: 45.28%). In

contrast, **AACS** demonstrates a more responsive behavior (lowest omission: 28.57%) but at the cost of high commission (23.08%), suggesting possible over-detection or misclassification. Interestingly, when shrub clearing events are included as valid change, AACS's commission error drops to 18%, reinforcing the hypothesis that the product may have captured such events but they were excluded from the reference.

EFDA reports the highest omission (54.35%) and lowest overall accuracy (94.96%), reflecting challenges in detecting even abrupt change types. On the other hand, the **Harmonized products** achieve a strong balance: 96.75% overall accuracy, no commission for change, and an omission rate of 32.08%. These results validate the potential of harmonization methodologies to combine sensitivity and reliability across multiple data sources.

Table 3. Validation metrics for the product-specific definition

Product	Overall Accuracy (%)	No Change. Omission error (%)	No Change. Commission error (%)	Change. Omission error (%)	Change. Commission error (%)
Landsat	95.41	0.00	4.86	45.28	0.00
Sentinel	95.22	1.28	3.93	35.85	15.00
GFC	97.99	0.00	2.08	35.71	0.00
EFDA	94.96	0.21	5.06	54.35	4.55
AACS	97.19	1.28	1.69	28.57	23.08
Harmonized. Source Priority	96.75	0.00	3.49	32.08	0.00
Harmonized. Class Priority	96.75	0.00	3.49	32.08	0.00

Original native products "Landsat": annual disturbance maps from Landsat time series; change classes = clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, wildfire. "Sentinel": annual disturbance maps from Sentinel-2 time series; change classes = clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, wildfire. "GFC": Global Forest Change; change class: tree loss. "EFDA": European Forest Disturbance Atlas; change classes = harvest, wildfire and wind. "AACS": Alert and Annual Change System (Spain); national vector product; change classes = vegetation loss and wildfire.

Harmonized products, built from EFDA, Landsat, Sentinel-2, AACS, and GFC under two fusion schemes. Strategy A (source-priority): majority voting with fixed source hierarchy. Strategy B (class-priority): majority voting with a class; change classes = clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, wildfire.

A complementary validation approach was implemented using **pixel-level detection metrics**. These metrics focus on spatial detection patterns, including whether a product flagged any disturbed pixels within a reference polygon, how much of the area was affected, and whether the timing of the detection aligned with the actual event. This analysis offers a more sensitive view

of each product's behavior and helps explain apparent inconsistencies between detection performance and matrix-derived omission or commission errors.

Landsat achieves the highest detection rate (95.0%) and the greatest average detection area (52.7%), yet still reports a substantial omission error for change (45.3%) in the confusion matrix. This apparent contradiction reflects the different thresholds inherent to each approach: detecting even a small number of disturbed pixels within a polygon suffices for pixel-level detection, but not necessarily to shift the polygon's majority class to "change" in matrix-based validation.

A similar—but more balanced—pattern is observed for **Sentinel-2**, which shows a detection rate of 86.2% and comparable spatial sensitivity (51.3%). Its omission error (35.9%) is notably lower than Landsat's, suggesting that Sentinel detections are often more spatially cohesive—enough to alter the dominant class. However, this comes at the cost of a higher commission error (15.0%) for change. **GFC** shows a substantial omission error (35.7%) and a lower detection rate (75%). This reflects its core limitation: by design, GFC reports only the first disturbance event detected per pixel, ignoring subsequent changes. Over time, and particularly in dynamic landscapes, this results in under-detection. **EFDA** also illustrates a conservative detection approach. Although it achieves a respectable detection rate (86%), its average detection area is lower (43.2%), and it exhibits the highest omission error for change (54.4%) among all products. This suggests that EFDA frequently fails to map a sufficient share of disturbed pixels within a given polygon to trigger a majority-class change—reflecting a low-sensitivity but high-precision design philosophy.

Table 4. Summary of Pixel-Level Detection Metrics (2020–2023)

Product	Detection Rate (%)	Avg. Detection Area (%)	Mean Temporal Accuracy (years)	False Positive Rate (%)
Landsat	95.00	52.65	0.43	0.35
Sentinel	86.21	51.26	0.30	0.83
GFW	75.00	45.04	0.40	6.77
EFDA	86.00	43.23	0.60	0.29
AACS	60.00	42.74	0.80	0.36

4.1.1.2 Abrupt change. Restrictive definition

The second configuration applies a **stricter reference**, including only clear-cutting and fire. This scenario is designed to isolate performance for **abrupt, high-severity disturbances**, which are typically easier to detect. As expected, all products improve in overall accuracy (gains of 1–3 percentage points), and commission errors decrease for those previously penalized by broader interpretations. **Harmonized maps excel** under these conditions, showing near-perfect accuracy and minimal omission. Meanwhile, some products such as Sentinel and AACS continue to incur

high commission errors, suggesting that their detection algorithms remain sensitive to disturbances not included in this narrower typology.

Overall accuracy increases across all products. **Harmonized maps** achieve the best performance (99%), cutting omission errors for change to 17.86% and maintaining zero commission. **Landsat** and **GFC** retain their conservative profiles, with omission around 32–35% but no false positives for change.

EFDA's omission improves slightly (to 46.43%) while commission drops to 6.25%, indicating a slight performance gain under a simpler disturbance framework. **Sentinel** and **AACS**, in contrast, exhibit high commission errors (24% and 23%, respectively), suggesting they continue to flag events (e.g. thinning or shrub clearing) excluded from this definition.

Table 5. Validation metrics for the change restricted definition (clear-cutting and fire)

Product	Overall Accuracy (%)	No Change. Omission error (%)	No Change. Commission error (%)	Change. Omission error (%)	Change. Commission error (%)
Landsat	98.19	0.00	1.88	32.14	0.00
Sentinel	96.99	1.28	1.90	32.14	24.00
GFC	97.99	0.00	2.08	35.71	0.00
EFDA	97.19	0.21	2.70	46.43	6.25
AACS	97.19	1.28	1.69	28.57	23.08
Harmonized. Source Priority	99.00	0.00	1.05	17.86	0.00
Harmonized. Class Priority	99.00	0.00	1.05	17.86	0.00

4.1.1.3 Inclusive definition

The third validation test expands the definition of change to include thinning, simulating **more gradual and spatially fragmented canopy disturbances** common in Mediterranean forest management. This broader interpretation increases the difficulty of detection, particularly for sensors or algorithms optimized for abrupt changes. Most products experience declines in overall accuracy and marked increases in omission. AACS and EFDA are the most affected, with omission rates nearing or exceeding 50%. Only the Harmonized products maintain stable performance, with omission errors below 26% and zero commission, confirming their resilience and generalizability under complex conditions.

Including thinning increases omission errors for all products. **AACS**, which previously performed well, now shows a drop in reliability: omission rises to 47.83% and commission remains high (20%),

indicating limited sensitivity to gradual changes. **EFDA** suffers most (54.35% omission), consistent with earlier tests.

Landsat and **Sentinel** exhibit a moderate decline in performance (omission: 41.30% and 34.78%), yet maintain zero or low commission errors. This confirms their utility in detecting change, albeit with underestimation of extent in more subtle interventions.

The **Harmonized products** remain the most robust: overall accuracy above 97.6%, omission below 26%, and no commission errors. These results reinforce the effectiveness of harmonization strategies when applied to heterogeneous and complex disturbance typologies.

The progression from product-specific to inclusive definitions reveals several key patterns:

- **Commission errors** remain stable or decrease when the change definition is broadened, as detections previously considered false positives are reclassified as valid.
- **Omission errors**, however, increase for nearly all products when thinning is included, exposing difficulties in capturing subtle changes.
- **Harmonized maps** consistently outperform others by maintaining **low omission and zero commission** under all change definitions.
- **AACS**, although initially strong, exhibits a notable drop in accuracy under broader definitions.
- **GFC's omission remains constant** in applicable scenarios due to its structural limitation of recording only a single disturbance per pixel.

While **Landsat, Sentinel, and Harmonized products use the same source classes**, they behave differently in Tables 4 and 5. This is explained by the **design of the harmonization process**, which imposes stricter criteria for labelling change. In particular:

- The **harmonization applies voting rules** where at least two sources must agree to detect change.
- Class prioritization or source prioritization is used to resolve conflicts (depending on the strategy), avoiding errors propagated from any single dataset.
- **Fire from AACS is always prioritized**, but shrub clearing or thinning is more cautiously labeled unless strongly supported.
- EFDA logging is **probabilistically assigned** to clear-cutting or canopy decrease using severity distributions and Bayesian classification, further increasing thematic consistency.

Thanks to these mechanisms, Harmonized layers are able to **filter out isolated detections of shrub clearing or thinning** that may otherwise appear as false positives in Landsat or Sentinel. This explains why, even using the same base data, the Harmonized layers achieve significantly **lower commission errors and more stable performance** under stricter definitions of change.

Table 6. Validation metrics for the binary scheme “Change vs. No change” (Change = aggregated disturbance). For each product evaluated the table reports: Overall Accuracy (%); Omission and Commission error (%) for the No-change class; and Omission and Commission error (%) for the Change class, where change is the union of all disturbance types. Errors are expressed as percentages relative to the reference data and quantify missed detections (omission) and false alarms (commission).

Product	Overall Accuracy (%)	No Change. Omission error (%)	No Change. Commission error (%)	Change. Omission error (%)	Change. Commission error (%)
Landsat	96.32	0.00	3.89	41.30	0.00
Sentinel	96.51	0.43	3.31	34.78	6.25
GFC					
EFDA	94.96	0.21	5.06	54.35	4.55
AACS	94.57	1.28	4.53	47.83	20.00
Harmonized. Source Priority	97.67	0.00	2.49	26.09	0.00
Harmonized. Class Priority	97.87	0.00	2.29	23.91	0.00

Original native products “Landsat”: annual disturbance maps from Landsat time series; change classes = clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, wildfire. “Sentinel”: annual disturbance maps from Sentinel-2 time series; change classes = clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, wildfire. “EFDA”: European Forest Disturbance Atlas; change classes = harvest, wildfire and wind. “AACS”: Alert and Annual Change System (Spain); change classes = vegetation loss and wildfire.

Harmonized products. built from EFDA, Landsat, Sentinel-2, AACS, and GFC under two fusion schemes. Strategy A (source-priority): majority voting with fixed source hierarchy. Strategy B (class-priority): majority voting with a class; change classes = clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, wildfire.

4.1.2 Specific operational horizon for each product

To complement the comparative analysis over the common period (2020–2023), each map was also evaluated within the specific temporal window for which it was designed and for which reference data was available. Table 6 presents the corresponding validation metrics for Landsat, GFC, and EFDA.

Landsat, validated for the period 2018–2023, maintains high overall accuracy (94.18%) and reports no commission error for change. However, it still misses 40% of known change events (omission error), indicating that even within its optimal range, Landsat tends to under-report disturbances—likely due to its conservative classification thresholds. Its low commission for *no change* (6.37%) confirms a high level of precision, making it a reliable product for applications where false alarms must be minimized.

GFC, evaluated over its full coverage from 2000 to 2023, yields the lowest overall accuracy (70.54%) among the three. While it avoids commission errors for *change* and correctly classifies *no change* areas without omission, it suffers from very high omission (77.30%) and an unusually high

commission rate for *no change* (32.18%). These results reflect a core limitation of GFC's design: it only reports the **first disturbance event** detected in a pixel. Any subsequent changes—such as post-fire salvage logging, repeated fires, or secondary thinning—are not recorded. Over an extended temporal span like two decades, this one-event constraint causes a growing mismatch.

EFDA, which also spans 2000–2023, performs slightly better than GFC, with an overall accuracy of 74.12%. It detects more change events (change omission: 64.41%) but still misses the majority. Commission errors are higher than Landsat's (7.08% for change; 29.14% for no change), suggesting a tendency to over-label subtle or ambiguous disturbances.

Table 7. Validation metrics for the product-specific definition and the temporal period for which maps were created and reference data available.

Product	Overall Accuracy (%)	No Change. Omission error (%)	No Change. Commission error (%)	Change. Omission error (%)	Change. Commission error (%)
Landsat (2018-2023)	94.18	0.00	6.37	40.00	0.00
GFC (2000-2023)	70.54	0.00	32.18	77.30	0.00
EFDA (2000-2023)	74.12	1.70	29.14	64.41	7.08

Original native products "Landsat": annual disturbance maps from Landsat time series; change classes = clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, wildfire. "EFDA": European Forest Disturbance Atlas; change classes = harvest, wildfire and wind. "GFC": Global Forest Change; change classes = tree cover loss.

4.2 Thematic Change Classification Accuracy

This table provides a disaggregated evaluation of disturbance detection accuracy for Landsat, Sentinel, and the Harmonized products, using the complete classification schema: no change, clear-cutting, thinning, shrub clearing, and wildfire. It moves beyond binary change assessment to assess how well each product performs per disturbance type.

Across all products, no change areas are mapped with high reliability. Landsat and both Harmonized maps achieve perfect producer accuracy, with Sentinel only slightly lower (98.72%). User accuracy is also consistently above 95%, confirming these products' ability to avoid false positives in undisturbed areas.

The detection of **clear-cutting** yields more variation. While Landsat and Sentinel capture these events with moderate accuracy (PA 59.09% and 63.64%, respectively), the Harmonized maps perform better (PA 68.18%) and achieve near-perfect user accuracy (100% and 93.75%). This pattern suggests that the **harmonization process**, by consolidating multiple sources, **enhances** recall for clear-cutting without introducing false detections.

Thinning, which represents more gradual and spectrally subtle canopy reductions, remains a weak point across all maps. Landsat and Sentinel show low producer accuracy (27.78% and 38.39%, respectively), with the Harmonized layers offering modest improvement (PA 44.44% in source-priority). Although these values remain far from ideal, the upward trend indicates that fusion strategies can slightly increase sensitivity to this challenging class.

Shrub clearing is virtually undetected in all products. Sentinel achieves minimal performance (PA 14.29%, UA 16.67%), while Harmonized layers and Landsat fail entirely (PA 0%). This can be explained by the nature of shrub clearing: small-scale, spectrally heterogeneous, and often underrepresented in the input products. In the Harmonized maps, the strict requirement for change confirmation by at least two sources likely filters out most shrub clearing events, prioritizing thematic consistency.

Fire detection, in contrast, is strong across all products in terms of sensitivity: producer accuracy reaches 83.33% for Landsat and Sentinel, and 100% in the Harmonized maps. However, the user accuracy for Harmonized maps drops (66.67% and 75.00%), in contrast to 83.33% for both Landsat and Sentinel.

Table 8. Validation metrics for type of change. Note: UA: user’s accuracy (%) and PA: producer’s accuracy (%)

	Class									
	No change		Clear-cutting		Thinning		Shrub clearing		Wildfire	
	PA	UA	PA	UA	PA	UA	PA	UA	PA	UA
Landsat	100	95.14	59.09	100	27.78	55.56	0.00	0.00	83.33	83.33
Sentinel	98.72	96.07	63.64	87.50	38.39	58.33	14.29	16.67	83.33	83.33
Harmonized. Source Priority	100	96.51	68.18	100	44.44	72.73	0.00	0.00	100	66.67
Harmonized. Class Priority	100	96.51	68.18	93.75	38.39	63.64	0.00	0.00	100	66.67

This table simplifies the classification into three operational categories—no change, harvest, and wildfire—allowing direct comparison between Landsat, Sentinel, EFDA, and the Harmonized maps. By grouping disturbance types, particularly clear-cutting and thinning under harvest, the analysis aligns more closely with products like EFDA and provides an aggregate view of detection capacity.

Harvest detection exhibits considerable variability across products. EFDA shows the lowest sensitivity, with only 32.5% of reference harvest events correctly identified. However, its relatively high user accuracy (86.67%) suggests that when EFDA does report a harvest, it is generally correct—yet the majority of real events remain undetected. Landsat demonstrates stronger precision (UA 100%), but still misses nearly half of actual harvest occurrences (PA 52.5%). Sentinel substantially improves recall (PA 70%) while maintaining acceptable precision (UA 94.59%), offering a more balanced performance between detection and reliability.

The Harmonized products deliver the strongest performance overall. This marked improvement in sensitivity, without any loss in precision, underscores the effectiveness of harmonization—particularly when thematic priorities guide the integration. The fusion of conservative inputs (e.g. EFDA, Landsat) with more sensitive datasets (e.g. Sentinel, AACS) results in a robust and consistent harvest layer that captures a wider spectrum of disturbance events.

Regarding wildfire detection, the Harmonized maps again achieve complete sensitivity (PA 100%). However, this comes at the expense of user accuracy, which drops to 75%. In contrast, Sentinel presents a more balanced profile, with perfect user accuracy (100%) and moderate producer accuracy (83.33%), indicating fewer false positives. EFDA underperforms in this class as well, with only 33.33% of fire events detected and low precision (UA 28.57%).

Table 9. Validation metrics for no change, harvest (clear-cutting and thinning) and fire. Note: UA: user's accuracy (%) and PA: producer's accuracy (%)

	Class					
	No change		Harvest		Wildfire	
	PA	UA	PA	UA	PA	UA
Landsat	100	96.11	52.50	100.00	83.33	83.33
Sentinel	99.57	96.69	62.50	92.59	83.33	100
EFDA	99.79	94.94	32.50	86.67	33.33	28.57
Harmonized. Source Priority	100	97.51	65	100	100	75.00
Harmonized. Class Priority	100	97,71	67,50	100	100	75,00

5 Conclusions

- **Harmonized products deliver superior and stable results**

The two harmonized disturbance maps—developed using **source-priority** and **class-priority** fusion strategies—outperform all individual products across all validation scenarios. Both achieve **0% commission error** in binary change detection and **omission rates below 32%**, demonstrating high consistency and robustness.

Their performance remains strong under varying definitions of change—from product-specific interpretations to **strict (clear-cutting and fire only)** with **omission rates smaller than 17%** or inclusive (adding thinning) frameworks—confirming their adaptability and operational value.

While **per-class producer and user accuracies (PA/UA)** of the harmonized products may appear only moderately better than those of the individual maps—particularly for clear-cutting and thinning—their superiority becomes clearer when evaluated at **aggregate levels**. The harmonized layers consistently translate pixel-level detections into correct unit-level classifications more effectively, resulting in **more balanced omission/commission trade-offs** and greater stability across spatial and thematic dimensions.

This result validates the harmonization approach, which integrates multiple datasets using spatial agreement rules, source hierarchies, and thematic prioritization to consolidate reliable detections and suppress isolated or ambiguous signals.

- **Thematic classification improves with harmonization but remains challenging for subtle classes**

While all maps achieve high accuracy for the “no change” class (producer accuracy >98%), performance declines for specific disturbance types. Clear-cutting is detected reasonably well (PA 59–68%), but thinning and especially shrub clearing remain difficult to classify accurately.

The harmonized layers improve detection of harvest events overall and show better performance for thinning (PA up to 44%), but shrub clearing remains underrepresented or undetected in all products.

This reflects ongoing limitations in capturing low-intensity, spectrally subtle, or spatially fragmented disturbances, even under harmonized frameworks.

- **Harmonization strategy affects thematic attribution in class-specific ways**

The two harmonization strategies developed in this project—**source-priority** and **class-priority**—achieve comparable overall performance, but their effects differ significantly across disturbance classes.

This is particularly evident in the case of **thinning**, a moderate-intensity disturbance class that is only explicitly detected by the internal Landsat and Sentinel-2 products. The **source-priority strategy yields higher producer (44%) and user (73%) accuracy** for thinning than class-priority (39% PA, 64% UA). This is because the source-priority approach, which assigns the final label

based on a predefined hierarchy of input datasets, **preserves the thinning labels provided by top-ranked sources**.

In contrast, the **class-priority strategy resolves conflicts based on thematic severity**, favouring classes like fire and clear-cutting over thinning. When multiple products detect change with different labels, thinning classifications are often overridden by more dominant ones, even if those are less accurate in the given context.

These results underscore that **harmonization strategies do not impact all disturbance types equally**.

- **Pixel- and unit-level metrics capture complementary aspects of map performance**

The comparison between **unit-level confusion matrices** and **pixel-based detection summaries** provides deeper insights into internal map behavior. Products such as **EFDA** and **Landsat** show high pixel-level detection rates ($\geq 86\%$ and $\geq 95\%$, respectively), but much lower unit-level reclassification, suggesting that although change is partially detected, it is not sufficient to trigger a full polygon-level assignment.

Conversely, **GFC**, despite a low detection rate, achieves moderate omission error, indicating that when it does detect change, it applies it more uniformly across space.

This highlights the value of using both metrics: unit-level accuracy captures operational reliability, while pixel-based analysis reveals sensitivity and internal consistency.

APPENDIX 1. Confusion matrices change no change

Table 10. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Landsat Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting and wildfires.

Product Landsat					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	470	9	479	98.12	1.88
Change		19	19	100.00	0.00
	470	28			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	67.86			
Omission Error (%)	0.00	32.14			
Overall Accuracy (%)			98.19%		

Table 11. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Sentinel-2 Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting and wildfires.

Product Sentinel-2					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	464	9	473	98.10	1.90
Change	6	19	25	76.00	24.00
	470	28			
Producer Accuracy (%)	98.72	67.86			
Omission Error (%)	1.28	32.14			
Overall Accuracy (%)			96.99%		

Table 12. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for GFC Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting and wildfires.

Product GFC					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	470	10	480	97.92	2.08
Change		18	18	100.00	0.00
	470	28			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	64.29			
Omission Error (%)	0.00	35.71			
Overall Accuracy (%)			97.99%		

Table 13. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for EFDA Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting and wildfires.

Product EFDA					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	469	13	482	97.30	2.70
Change	1	15	16	93.75	6.25
	470	28			
Producer Accuracy (%)	99.79	53.57			
Omission Error (%)	0.21	46.43			
Overall Accuracy (%)			97.19%		

Table 14. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for AACS Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting and wildfires.

Product AACS					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	464	8	472	98.31	1.69
Change	6	20	26	76.92	23.08
	470	28			
Producer Accuracy (%)	98.72	71.43			
Omission Error (%)	1.28	28.57			
Overall Accuracy (%)			97.19%		

Table 15. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Source Priority Harmonized Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting and wildfires.

Product Source Priority Harmonized					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	470	5	475	98.95	1.05
Change		23	23	100.00	0.00
	470	28			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	82.14			
Omission Error (%)	0.00	17.86			
Overall Accuracy (%)			99.00%		

Table 16. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Class Priority Harmonized Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting and wildfires.

Product Class Priority Harmonized					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	470	5	475	98.95	1.05
Change		23	23	100.00	0.00
	470	28			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	82.14			
Omission Error (%)	0.00	17.86			
Overall Accuracy (%)			99.00%		

APPENDIX 2. Confusion matrices change no change

Table 17. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Landsat Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting, thinning and wildfires.

Product Landsat					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	470	19	489	96.11	3.89
Change		27	27	100.00	0.00
	470	46			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	58.70			
Omission Error (%)	0.00	41.30			
Overall Accuracy (%)			96.32%		

Table 18. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Sentinel-2 Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting, thinning and wildfires.

Product Sentinel-2					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	468	16	484	96.69	3.31
Change	2	30	32	93.75	6.25
	470	46			
Producer Accuracy (%)	99.57	65.22			
Omission Error (%)	0.43	34.78			
Overall Accuracy (%)			96.51%		

Table 19. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for EFDA Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting, thinning and wildfires.

Product EFDA					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	469	25	494	94.94	5.06
Change	1	21	22	95.45	4.55
	470	46			
Producer Accuracy (%)	99.79	45.65			
Omission Error (%)	0.21	54.35			
Overall Accuracy (%)			94.96%		

Table 20. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for AACS Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting, thinning and wildfires.

Product AACS					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	464	22	486	95.47	4.53
Change	6	24	30	80.00	20.00
	470	46			
Producer Accuracy (%)	98.72	52.17			
Omission Error (%)	1.28	47.83			
Overall Accuracy (%)			94.57%		

Table 21. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Source Priority Harmonized Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting, thinning and wildfires.

Product Source Priority Harmonized					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	470	12	482	97.51	2.49
Change		34	34	100.00	0.00
	470	46			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	73.91			
Omission Error (%)	0.00	26.09			
Overall Accuracy (%)			97.67%		

Table 22. Confusion Matrix and Accuracy Metrics for Class Priority Harmonized Product (2020–2023 Validation Period). Note reference change classes included clear-cutting, thinning and wildfires.

Product Class Priority Harmonized					
	No change	Change	Total	User Accuracy (%)	Commission Error (%)
No change	470	11	481	97.71	2.29
Change		35	35	100.00	0.00
	470	46			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	76.09			
Omission Error (%)	0.00	23.91			
Overall Accuracy (%)			97.87%		

APPENDIX 3. Confusion matrices type of change

Table 23. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for Landsat Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Harvest, Wildfires). Note Harvest include clear-cutting and thinning reference points.

Product Landsat	No Change	Harvest	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	470	18	1	489	96.11
Harvest		21		21	100
Wildfires		1	5	6	83.33
Total	470	40	6		
Producer Accuracy (%)	100	67.50	83.33		
Overall Accuracy (%)				96.12	

Table 24. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for Sentinel Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Harvest, Wildfires). Note Harvest include clear-cutting and thinning reference points.

Product Sentinel-2	No Change	Harvest	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	468	15	1	484	96.69
Harvest	2	25		27	92.59
Wildfires			5	5	100
Total	470	40			
Producer Accuracy (%)	99.57	62.50	83.33		
Overall Accuracy (%)				96.51	

Table 25. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for EFDA Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Harvest, Wildfires). Note Harvest include clear-cutting and thinning reference points.

Product EFDA	No Change	Harvest	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	469	22	3	494	94.94
Harvest	1	13	1	15	86.67
Wildfires		5	2	7	28.57
Total	470	40			
Producer Accuracy (%)	99.79	32.50	33.33		
Overall Accuracy (%)				93.80	

Table 26. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for the Source Priority Harmonized Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Harvest, Wildfires). Note Harvest include clear-cutting and thinning reference points.

Product Source Priority Harmonized	No Change	Harvest	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	470	12		482	97.51
Harvest		26		26	100.00
Wildfires		2	6	8	75.00
Total	470	40	6		
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	65.00	100.00		
Overall Accuracy (%)				97.29	

Table 27. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for the Class Priority Harmonized Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Harvest, Wildfires). Note Harvest include clear-cutting and thinning reference points.

Product Class Priority Harmonized	No Change	Harvest	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	470	11		482	97.71
Harvest		27		26	100.00
Wildfires		2	6	8	75.00
Total	470	40	6		
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	67,50	100.00		
Overall Accuracy (%)				97.48	

APPENDIX 4. Confusion matrices type of change

Table 28. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for Landsat Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Clear-Cutting, Thinning, Wildfires).

Product Landsat	No Change	Clear-Cutting	Thinning	Shrubland	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	470	4	13	6	1	494	95.14
Clear Cutting		13				13	100.00
Thinning		3	5	1		9	55.56
Shrubland		1				1	0.00
Wildfires		1			5	6	83.33
Total	470	22	18	7			
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	59.09	27.78	0.00	83.33		
Overall Accuracy (%)							94.26

Table 29. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for Sentinel-2 Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Clear-Cutting, Thinning, Wildfires).

Product Sentinel-2	No Change	Clear-Cutting	Thinning	Shrubland	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	464	4	10	4	1	483	96.07
Clear Cutting	1	14	1			16	87.50
Thinning	1	3	7	1		12	58.33
Shrubland	4	1		1		6	16.67
Wildfires				1	5	6	83.33
Total	470	22	18	7	6		
Producer Accuracy (%)	98.72	63.64	38.89	14.29	83.33		
Overall Accuracy (%)							93.88

Table 30. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for the Source Priority Harmonized Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Clear-Cutting, Thinning, Wildfires).

Product Source Harmonized	No Change	Clear-Cutting	Thinning	Shrubland	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	470	1	10	6		487	96.51
Clear Cutting		15				15	100.00
Thinning		3	8			11	72.73
Shrubland		1				1	0.00
Wildfires		2		1	6	9	66.67
Total	470	22	18	7	6		
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	68.18	44.44	0.00	100.00		
Overall Accuracy (%)							95.41

Table 31. Thematic Accuracy Assessment for the Class Priority Harmonized Product by Disturbance Type (No Change, Clear-Cutting, Thinning, Wildfires).

Product Class Harmonized	No Change	Clear-Cutting	Thinning	Shrubland	Wildfires	Total	User Accuracy (%)
No Cambio	470	1	10	6		487	96.51
Clear Cutting		15	1			16	93.75
Thinning		4	7			11	63.64
Shrubland							0.00
Wildfires		2			6	8	66.67
Total	470	22	18	7	6		
Producer Accuracy (%)	100.00	68.18	38.89	0.00	100.00		
Overall Accuracy (%)							95.22

APPENDIX 5. Examples of changes mapped as no change

<p>Plot ID 7569. Missing Product: Landsat Sentinel-2 GFC EFDA AACS</p>		
<p>Plot ID 7611. Missing Product: Landsat, Sentinel-2, AACS</p>		
<p>Plot ID 7611. Missing Product: Landsat, Sentinel-2, AACS</p>		

<p>Plot ID 7863. Missing Product: Landsat, Sentinel-2</p>		
<p>Plot ID 3402. Missing Product: Sentinel-2</p>		
<p>Plot ID 2431. Missing Product: GFC AACS</p>		
<p>Plot ID 5347. Missing Product: GFC, EFDA, AACS</p>		
<p>Plot ID 798. Missing Product: EFDA AACS</p>		

APPENDIX 6. Detection Rate by Disturbance Size Class

Proportion of detected disturbance events by size class for each product. This table presents the percentage of reference disturbance polygons detected by each product, stratified by polygon size.

Size Class	Sentinel	Landsat	GFC	AACS	EFDA
< 0.2 ha	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.2–1 ha	66.67	77.78	55.56	0.00	44.44
> 1 ha	91.67	95.83	58.33	75.00	93.75

Interpretation notes:

This analysis includes all reference disturbance types—including shrub clearing and thinning, which are not explicitly detectable by GFC, AACS, or EFDA. These results should therefore be interpreted with caution and not considered as purely spatial resolution effects.